

Leukoplakia Managed By 980 nm Diode Laser : A Case Report

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Abstract

Leukoplakia is the most common oral potentially malignant disorder encountered in clinical practice. The previous term pre-cancerous lesion was replaced by oral potentially malignant disorder in 2007 and defined as “It is the risk of malignancy being present in a lesion or condition either during the time of initial diagnosis or at a future date”¹. The definition was reframed again in 2020 as “any oral mucosal abnormality that is associated with a statistically increased risk of developing oral cancer”².

“Leukoplakia should be used to recognize white plaques of questionable risk having excluded (other) known diseases or disorders that carry no increased risk for cancer”³. Tobacco seems to be most important etiology for leukoplakia. Clinically it can vary in clinical presentation, that can be thin leukoplakia, homogenous leukoplakia, nodular and speckled leukoplakia. Biopsy is gold standard for histopathological confirmation.⁴

The treatment of the leukoplakia begins with the counseling to quit tobacco consumption in any form.⁵ A (Ask, Advise, Assess, Assist, Arrange) principle must be advocated⁴. Non surgical treatment of leukoplakia includes topical Tretinoin / Isotretinoin, topical Bleomycin, 13-cRA (cis retinoic acid) and Photodynamic Therapy. Chemo preventive agents such as vitamins (A, C, E), fenretinide (Vitamin A analogue), carotenoids (beta carotene, lycopene), green tea and curcumin are also beneficial. Chemoprevention trials on oral leukoplakia have had various methodological limitations and adverse events and have not provided any strong evidence of success. Surgical treatment includes excisional surgery, electrocauterization, laser surgery, or cryosurgery.⁵

Excision of precancerous oral lesions using LASER offers comparative advantages over traditional scalpel excision. These advantages include Lesser discomfort, Minimal intraoperative bleeding thus offering a clear surgical field, Disinfection of surgical site, faster healing without scarring and Minimal post-operative pain^{6,7}. Thus

we are presenting a case of leukoplakia treated with 980 diode laser.

Case Presentation

A 40-year-old male patient reported to our department with chief complaint of a white patch on his right cheek since 2 years. There was no similar family history and no history of trauma or surgery. The patient's medical and dental histories were non-contributory. Patient reported habit of chewing tobacco, 10 packets per day past 5 years. Patient also gives history of keeping tobacco on the same complaint region. On clinical examination, a solitary white patch with slight melanin pigmentation with a wrinkled surface and irregular margins was visible on the left buccal mucosa and vestibule extending from the second molar to the first premolar, measuring approximately 3 cm posterior-anteriorly and 1.5 cm superior-inferiorly in dimensions. The lesion extends to vestibular region. It was not tender on palpation. The lesion was non-scrapable and was having crack mud appearance, the surrounding mucosa appeared to be normal [Fig-1]. On the basis of clinical history a provisional diagnosis of Homogenous Leukoplakia was made. Toluidine blue staining was negative. Patient counseling was done and the patient was asked to completely quit the habit of smoking tobacco. They were motivated by

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way of the 5A principle (Ask, Advise, Assess, Assist and Arrange). The antioxidants were advised as chemoprophylactic measures for a month. According to the routine protocol, we had recommended topical anti-fungal agents for 10 days before the laser treatment. Perilesional infiltration of local anaesthetic was applied.

A diode laser at 980-nm wavelength (Ga-Al-As, DILAS, Germany) (Model: IndiLase, MEDSOL, Hosur, India), operating in a continuous mode with an output power of 2.0 W and a flexible 400mm diameter optic fibre (polyamide, 400 microfibers; Medfibers) equipped with a handpiece, was used. The energy produced at the target site varied according to the size of the lesion. Typically, the energy transmitted to the tissue was 1600J/cm². The aseptic conditions were maintained, and protective eyeglasses were given to both patients and operators. Laser ablation was performed with 1mm depth [Fig-2]. LASER beam was used in continuous mode in a paint brush manner. The LASER tip was used in direct contact mode with tissue to be ablated. The wound was left to heal by secondary intention. The patient was advised to take capsule amoxicillin 500 mg three times daily and tablet diclofenac 50 mg for 3 days. He was reviewed after 1 month, 3month and 1 year [Fig-3]. Healing was good and No complications or recurrence were noted.

Discussion

Various treatments modalities have been employed to eradicate leukoplakia, but it is challenging to eliminate due to the chances of recurrences and incomplete response. Antioxidants are widely used in potentially malignant disorder and cancerous lesion. These usually scavenge free radicals thus preventing free radical-induced carcinogenesis. Moreover topical retinoids also have been utilized in various studies. The results of previous studies have appreciated recurrences after withdrawal in approximately 50% of the cases⁴.

A laser is a device that emits light through a process of optical amplification based on the stimulated emission of electromagnetic radiation. Laser is an acronym, which stands for "Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation". The LASER light is emitted in an organized manner rather than in a random pattern as from a light bulb. Compared to sunlight and incandescent bulb laser light is Monochromatic, Coherent, Collimated and unidirectional.

Laser offers many advantages over other conventional methods: increased patient comfort, bloodless dry operating field, bactericidal effect, lesser post-operative pain, lesser chances of scarring, lesser post-operative swelling and minimal local anaesthesia and lesser recurrence rate than scalpel surgery. Diode laser has an additional biostimulatory effect compared to other laser, which increases growth promoting tissue.^{6,7}

Carbon dioxide (CO₂), neodymium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (Nd: YAG), diode, and erbium-doped yttrium aluminum garnet lasers (Er:YAG) have been used successfully to manage leukoplakia in previous literature. Thus we have chosen diode laser ablation in this case.⁴

Laser ablation is the superficial removal of the lesion, including a margin of clinically healthy mucosa while laser excision is the removal of lesion deeply, considers an excisional biopsy. Laser excision usually advised for non homogenous leukoplakia and leukoplakia of high risk site. In our case buccal mucosa and vestibule was involved with negative vital staining, thus laser ablation was planned.⁸

There were no recurrences or malignant transformation in the follow up period of 1 year. A regular follow-up is mandatory for these cases to evaluate any recurrences. Recurrences may also be related to patient's gender, non-cooperation to quit the habit, dysplastic activity, location of the lesion and the presence of lesion for a prolonged period. Recurrence rate of leukoplakia after laser treatment varies from literature to literature, varies from 29.3% (Ishii et al⁹), 17.5 (Yang et al¹⁰), 16.5%, (Paglioni et al¹¹) and 19.48% (Shivhare P et al¹²). A study by Ishii et al.⁹ reported malignant transformation in leukoplakia occurring even after laser evaporation over period of 5 years. Different studies showed malignant transformation rates of 4.12% and 11.4% after laser treatment^{9,10}. Thus, long follow-up is necessary to report malignant transformation in these cases.

Conclusion

Leukoplakia is most commonly encountered oral potentially malignant disorder, which is very well known for its malignant transformation. Early diagnosis and prompt treatment is the key to eliminate chances of malignant transformation. Diode laser can be a promising treatment modality for such cases with high success rate.

Figure 1 - Clinical presentation of the lesion

Figure 2 - Immediate Post-operative View

Figure 3 - Complete Healing After 1-1.5 months

References

1. Warnakulasuriya S, Newell W, Van der Waal I. Nomenclature and classification of potentially malignant disorders of the oral mucosa. *J Oral Pathol Med* 2007;36:575-80.
2. Warnakulasuriya S, Kujan O, Aguirre-Urizar JM, Bagan JV, González-Moles MÁ, Kerr AR, et al. Oral potentially malignant disorders: A consensus report from an international seminar on nomenclature and classification, convened by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer. *Oral Dis* 2021;27:1862-80.
3. Warnakulasuriya S. Clinical features and presentation of oral potentially malignant disorders. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol* 2018;125:582-90.
4. Shivhare P, Parihar A. Oral potentially malignant disorder. In: Shivhare P, Parihar A, editors. *Textbook of Oral Medicine and Radiology*. 2nd ed. Hyderabad: Paras Publisher; 2021. p. 218-58.
5. Swain SK, Debta P. Nonsurgical treatment of oral cavity leukoplakia. *Matrix Sci Med* 2020;4:91-5.
6. Shivhare P, Haidry N, Sah N, Kumar A, Gupta A, Singh A, Penumatcha MR, Subramanyam S. Comparative Evaluation of Efficacy and Safety of the Diode Laser (980 nm) and Sclerotherapy for the Treatment of Oral Pyogenic Granuloma. *Int J Dent*. 2022 Sep 17;2022:-8269221.
7. Shivhare P, Haidry N, Sah N, Kumar A, Gupta A, Singh A, Penumatcha MR, Subramanyam S. Comparative Evaluation of Efficacy and Safety of the Diode Laser (980 nm) and Sclerotherapy in the Treatment of Oral Vascular Malformations. *Int J Vasc Med*. 2022 Sep 5;2022:2785859.
8. Shivhare P, Parihar A. Advanced therapies in oral medicine. In: Shivhare P, Parihar A, editors. *Textbook of Oral Medicine and Radiology*. 2nd ed. Hyderabad: Paras Publisher; 2021. p. 858-74.
9. Ishii J, Fujita K, Munemoto S, Komori T. Management of oral leukoplakia by laser surgery: Relation between recurrence and malignant transformation and clinicopathological features. *J Clin Laser Med Surg* 2004;22:27-33.
10. Yang SW, Tsai CN, Lee YS, Chen TA. Treatment outcome of dysplastic oral leukoplakia with carbon dioxide laser – Emphasis on the factors affecting recurrence. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* 2011;69:e78-87.
11. de Pauli Paglioni M, Migliorati CA, Schausltz Pereira Faustino I, Linhares Almeida Mariz BA, Oliveira Corrêa Roza AL, Agustin Vargas P, et al. Laser excision of oral leukoplakia: Does it affect recurrence and malignant transformation? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Oral Oncol* 2020;109:104850.
12. Shivhare P, Haidry N, Kumar A, Parihar A, Singh A, Subramanyam S. Diode laser in the management of Leukoplakia - A retrospective study. *Ann Maxillofac Surg* 2022;12:178-84

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